

580 Appendix A: Comparison to simulations

581 Table [A.1](#) summarizes the success rate between the observations
582 and the different models discussed in section [5](#). Figures [A.1](#) and
583 [A.2](#) show examples of the comparison with the PIC simulations,
584 Figs. [A.3](#) and [A.4](#) show examples of the comparison with the
585 TEMZ simulations, and Figs. [A.5–A.9](#), [A.10](#) examples of the
586 comparison with the TEMZ+PIC simulations for three different
587 normalized simulated light curves (see Table [A.1](#)).

Table A.1. Success rates (in percent) between observed and simulated light curves.

Model	Π Distr.	Π Fl. Dur.	Π Fl. Ampl.	ψ Dur.	ψ Abs. ampl.	ψ Abs. rate
PIC (120min)	0	97	2	85	8	30
TEMZ	0	100	55	60	0	0
PIC + TEMZ (norm. 1)	3	98	13	5	0	0
PIC + TEMZ (norm 2)	3	96	31	4	1	0
PIC + TEMZ (norm. 3)	3	95	9	6	1	0

Notes. The columns are (1) Π distribution; (2) Π flare duration; (3) Π flare amplitude; (4) ψ inversion duration; (5) ψ absolute inversion amplitude; (6) ψ absolute inversion rate. For the combined PIC + TEMZ comparison, we are listing three cases. For the case “Norm. 1,” both models are normalized between [0,1]. For the case “Norm 2,” PIC is normalized between [0,1] and TEMZ normalized to the PIC light curve, and for the case “Norm 3” TEMZ is normalized between [0,1] and PIC normalized to the TEMZ light curve. For the PIC simulations, we chose the time step that produces the best agreement with the observations.

Fig. A.1. Example light curve for the PIC simulations with a 120 m time step. The panels from top to bottom show the observed Π , the simulated Π , the observed ψ , the simulated ψ , and the adjusted simulated ψ . The original simulations are shown in yellow, and the simulated light curves that match the observed cadence are shown in blue.

Fig. A.2. Histograms of the comparison between the observed data and the PIC simulations for the light curves in Fig. A.1. The top row (left to right) shows Π flare duration, Π flare amplitude, and Π distribution. The bottom row (left to right) shows ψ inversion duration, ψ absolute inversion amplitude, and ψ absolute inversion rate. The observed data are shown in blue and the simulated in orange.

Fig. A.3. Example light curve for the TEMZ simulations. The panels are the same as in Fig. A.1.

Fig. A.4. Histograms of the comparison between the observed data and the TEMZ simulations for the light curves in Fig. A.3. The panels are the same as in Fig. A.2.

Fig. A.5. Example light curve for the PIC+TEMZ simulations (Norm 1). The panels are the same as in Fig. A.1

Fig. A.6. Histograms of the comparison between the observed data and the PIC+TEMZ simulations for the light curves in Fig. A.5. Panels as in Fig. A.2.

Fig. A.7. Example light curve for the PIC+TEMZ simulations (Norm 2). Panels as in Fig. A.1

Fig. A.8. Histograms of the comparison between the observed the PIC+TEMZ simulations for the light curves in Fig. A.7. The panels are the same as in Fig. A.2.

Fig. A.9. Example light curve for the PIC+TEMZ simulations (Norm 3). The panels are the same as in Fig. A.1

Fig. A.10. Histograms of the comparison between the observed the PIC+TEMZ simulations for the light curves in Fig. A.9. The panels are the same as in Fig. A.2.